

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

A hybrid fluid master-apprentice evolutionary algorithm for large-scale multiplicity flexible job shop scheduling with sequence-dependent setup time: supplemental material

Linshan Ding^a, Zailin Guan^a, Zhengmin Zhang^a, Weikang Fang^a, Zhipeng Chen^a and Lei Yue^{b*}

^aDepartment School of Mechanical Science and Engineering, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan, People's Republic of China

^bSchool of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering, Guangzhou University, Guangzhou, People's Republic of China

1. Solution encoding and decoding

In this section, an example denoted as Problem-1 is used to facilitate the discussion about the solution encoding and decoding of HFMAE. The Gantt chart of Problem-1 is shown in Fig. 1-(a). Then, the encoding of the initial solution of Problem-1 is described in Fig. 1-(b). In Fig. 1-(b), the operation sequence is obtained according to the completion time of each operation in Fig. 1-(a). The length of the operation sequence is equal to the total number of operations, represented as $J_o = \sum_{r=1}^R N_r J_r$. The decoding approaches include semi-active, active, non-delay, and hybrid schedules (Li and Gao 2016). The non-delay schedule is adopted in this article.

The decoding procedure is as follows:

The decoding procedure

Step1: Set $l = 1$.

Step2: Select the l^{th} operation (r, n, j, i) of the operation sequence in Fig. 1-(b).

Step3: Assign the operation (r, n, j) to the machine i .

Step4: Calculate the completion time c_{rnj} of the operation (r, n, j) .

Step5: If l is equal to the total number of operations ($l = J_o$), go to step7; otherwise, go to step6.

Step6: Set $l = l + 1$, and go to step2.

Step7: Calculate the makespan of the schedule as $C_{max} = \max\{c_{rnj}, \forall(r, n, j)\}$.

Figure 1. Gantt chart and the solution representation in HFMAE (Problem-1).

2. Parameter settings

In the HFMAE, six parameters $\{H, iter_{min}, length_{max}, length_{min}, D, g_{cycle}\}$ need to be set up. The parameters $length_{min}$ and $length_{max}$ are relate to J_o (the total number of operations) that are predetermined and set to be $J_o/2$ and J_o (Li, Pan, and Liang 2010). To set the remaining four parameters appropriately, the Taguchi method of design of experiment (DOE) (Montogery 2005) is adopted. Moreover, 5 small-scale instances $\{N \in [10, 50], I \in [5, 20]\}$ and 5 large-scale instances $\{N \in [50, 200], I \in [20, 30]\}$ are generated randomly. In Table 1, four levels of the four parameters are listed.

Table 1. Levels of the four parameters.

Parameters	Levels			
	1	2	3	4
H	5	10	15	20
$iter_{min}$	5	10	15	20
D	200	400	600	800
g_{cycle}	5	10	15	20

As shown in Table 2, the parameter combinations are represented with the orthogonal array L_{16} . In Table 2, the average makespan obtained through 30 independent replications is again averaged and grouped under small-scale and large-scale instances. The final average makespan of small-scale and large-scale instances are used as the response values which are represented as $C_{avg-small}$ and $C_{avg-large}$, respectively. Fig. 2 shows the factor level trend of small-scale and large-scale instances.

Then, $\{H = 20, iter_{min} = 20, D = 800, g_{cycle} = 5\}$ and $\{H = 5, iter_{min} = 15, D = 800, g_{cycle} = 15\}$ are chosen as the control parameters of small-scale and large-scale problems, respectively.

Table 2. Orthogonal array and average response values.

Combinations	Parameters				$C_{avg-small}$	$C_{avg-large}$
	H	$iter_{min}$	D	g_{cycle}		
1	5	5	200	5	642.0	1057.7
2	5	10	400	10	656.3	1051.0
3	5	15	600	15	646.7	1049.3
4	5	20	800	20	636.3	1050.0
5	10	5	400	15	642.0	1061.7
6	10	10	200	20	645.3	1055.0
7	10	15	800	5	632.3	1040.7
8	10	20	600	10	636.0	1057.3
9	15	5	600	20	641.7	1063.7
10	15	10	800	15	635.0	1047.0
11	15	15	200	10	649.3	1061.7
12	15	20	400	5	635.0	1057.7
13	20	5	800	10	636.7	1062.7
14	20	10	600	5	643.3	1059.7
15	20	15	400	20	636.0	1055.7
16	20	20	200	15	636.0	1048.0

Figure 2. The trend of the factor level of small-scale and large-scale instances.

3. Characteristics of generated datasets

In this section, the characteristics of generated datasets in the section “5.3 Experiments on generated datasets” is listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of cases with different scales and multiplicity.

Problem scale	Multiplicity (N_r)	Number of jobs	Number of machines	Number of alternative machines per operation (avg)	Total number of operations
---------------	---------------------------	-------------------	-----------------------	---	-------------------------------

Small-1	U (3, 10)	10	5	2	30
Small-2	U (3, 10)	15	10	4	60
Small-3	U (3, 10)	20	10	4	100
Small-4	U (10, 20)	30	15	6	180
Small-5	U (10, 20)	30	20	6	180
Large-1	U (10, 20)	50	20	8	250
Large-2	U (10, 20)	60	20	8	300
Large-3	U (20, 100)	100	25	10	600
Large-4	U (20, 100)	150	30	12	750
Large-5	U (20, 100)	200	30	12	1000

4. The Wilcoxon test considering generated datasets

In this section, the result of Wilcoxon test considering generated datasets in the section “5.3 Experiments on generated datasets” is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Wilcoxon test considering generated datasets.

HFMAE vs.	R^+	R^-	$p - value$
TS	55	0	0.000977
GA	54.5	0.5	0.004576
2SGA	54.5	0.5	0.004576
MAE	55	0	0.000977

References

- Li, J. Q., Q. K. Pan, and Y. C. Liang. 2010. "An effective hybrid tabu search algorithm for multi-objective flexible job-shop scheduling problems." Review of. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 59 (4):647-62. doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2010.07.014.
- Li, Xinyu, and Liang Gao. 2016. "An effective hybrid genetic algorithm and tabu search for flexible job shop scheduling problem." Review of. *International Journal of Production Economics* 174:93-110. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2016.01.016.
- Montgomery, D. C. 2005. "Design and analysis of experiments." Review of. *journal of the American Statistical* 81(16):308.